

Urban ReLeaf

Urban ReLeaf outreach, impact and exploitation report I

D6.3

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Short description	This is the mid-term exploitation point for Urban ReLeaf, including an overview of the key exploitation results, planned exploitation measure and possible impacts. The report also details next steps to further refine the exploitation plan.
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Project Partners

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Acronyms

AQ	Air Quality
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Consumer
B2G	Business to Government
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CIBOS	CIBOS Innovation
CLS	Collecte Localisation Satellites
CS	Citizen Science
CSO	Civil Society Organization
CoP	Community of Practice
DfB	Design for Business
DQ	Data Quality
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
IA	Impact Assessment
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
ICLEI	Local Governments for Sustainability
IIASA	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
NbS	Nature-based Solutions
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
R&I	Research & Innovation
TRH	Temperature and Relative Humidity
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UNIVDUN	University of Dundee
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WPs	Work Packages

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Executive Summary

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions and planning. This deliverable serves as a midterm assessment of the Urban ReLeaf project's outreach, impact, and exploitation pathways. As part of Work Package 6 (Dissemination, Exploitation, and Strategic Communication), it integrates key exploitable results across various work packages to ensure that project results are effectively communicated, utilised, and leveraged for future applications through exploitation measures. The key objectives include:

- Ensuring the broad outreach of project outcomes to in academia, policymakers, the public and industry.
- Maximising the socio-economic and environmental impacts of the project's results.
- Developing actionable pathways for exploitation, including scale-up and uptake by stakeholders, commercialisation, policy recommendations, and further research.

The deliverable builds upon the initial strategy for exploiting project results, utilising a value proposition methodology, applied through interactive workshops with the Urban ReLeaf consortium. The core of this exploitation plan is a comprehensive overview of the range of individual key exploitable results identified at this mid-stage. Specifically, it provides details on exploitation measures, target stakeholders, readiness, anticipated outcomes and impacts for each key exploitable result. This reveals substantial and cross-cutting opportunities for commercial, non-commercial and policy exploitation beyond the project's lifespan.

An additional key component of the deliverable is the future activities to refine exploitation in the remainder of the project. This includes plans for establishing ownership/intellectual property rights, a roadmap of future exploitation efforts, including workshops, Design for Business sprints and ongoing exploitation monitoring. This report sets the foundation for a second exploitation plan due at the end of Urban ReLeaf (M48), which will build on these findings and further refine the strategy for ensuring long-term social, scientific and economic impact.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background – the Urban ReLeaf project and city pilots

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. The project addresses the challenges of increasing environmental stresses in urban areas, accentuated inequalities in access to high-quality greenspace, lack of suitable data for planning and decision making as well as inclusion in public participation in science and research.

The main objectives of Urban ReLeaf are to:

- Understand current data ecosystem and urban greening and participation policies in six pilot cities and co-develop opportunities for citizen science and citizen participation to complement existing practices.
- Mobilise and empower local communities in issues of public interest surrounding urban green infrastructure and environmental stewardship.
- Support the long-term inclusion of active and passive data from citizens within official data streams for urban monitoring, planning and innovation in public policy.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and training across relevant actors beyond the six pilot cities by establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.
- Offer flexible and innovative ways of governance that can underpin inclusive green urban planning in support of the European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In pursuit of urban climate resilience, six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities co-create participatory, and data-driven innovations to democratise urban greenspace monitoring and the wider policy making process. Athens is undergoing a greening transformation with a new, citizen-powered tree registry providing critical data for better management of greenspaces. Cascais engages citizens in sharing perceptions and thermal comfort levels while using greenspaces to validate the effectiveness of its parks. Meanwhile in Dundee, a city facing increasing grey infrastructure in deprived areas, actions to enhance the accessibility of greenspaces are co-developed with citizens and stakeholders. Mannheim has a heat action plan to safeguard its most vulnerable residents but has identified critical data gaps. Citizen observations of trees and thermal comfort, when integrated with official data streams, will aid the delivery of climate adaptation measures. Riga engages diverse audiences to address concerns about air pollution and greenspace usage, to ensure better informed policies. Finally, in Utrecht, data on temperature, humidity and heat stress, collected by and for citizens, will help them shape effective mitigation strategies to reduce the urban heat island effect.

1.2 Purpose of the document

This deliverable provides a midterm assessment of the outreach, impact and exploitation pathways of Urban ReLeaf. Impact and collaboration are at the heart of the project, supporting cross-sectoral innovation and political agenda setting for

climate change adaptation and green blue infrastructure planning in urban environments. To achieve the projects objectives and ambitions, it is therefore essential to establish the exploitation and impact opportunities and pathways.

This deliverable is part of the Work Package 6 (WP6) Dissemination, Exploitation and Strategic Communication. This is the first of two exploitation reports (D6.3: Urban ReLeaf outreach, impact and exploitation report I; D6.6: Urban ReLeaf outreach, impact, and exploitation report II), with the final plan being produced at the end of the project (M48). As WP6 integrates the results of all the work packages, this deliverable is crosscutting (Figure 1). Additionally, this deliverable builds upon D6.1: Urban ReLeaf engagement, communication and dissemination plan and can be seen as the next step in the broader objectives of WP6.

The exploitation plan links the project's key exploitable results (KERs) with the expected outcomes and impacts of the project. Exploitation is inherently connected and linked with the development of dissemination activities. While dissemination makes the project's results visible, exploitation ensures its outcomes are effectively utilised, as an ongoing endeavour, both during and beyond project implementation.

The objectives of the deliverable are to:

1. Enhance effective outreach and knowledge transfer of the projects KERs to stakeholders, including academia, policymakers, the public and industry.
2. Maximise the socio-economic and environmental impacts of the project outcomes.
3. Develop and identify new actionable exploitation measures and pathways for utilising project results, including commercialisation, policy recommendations, and further research.
4. Develop a clear plan and next steps for future activities to refine the exploitation of Urban ReLeaf, including monitoring.

The exploitation plan ensures a lasting project legacy by leveraging KERs, novel opportunities, additional stakeholders and wider transferability beyond the project's lifespan. It stimulates the uptake and evolution of Urban ReLeaf use-cases, data, technology, know-how, learning and tools across and beyond all six pilot cities. The plan also promotes wider adoption by policy, public and research end-users, while providing guidance for IP management, pathways to commercialisation and broader value creation. Simply put, it demonstrates the added value of Urban ReLeaf to society, and how it will be achieved.

Figure 1: Urban ReLeaf Interdependencies of Work Packages

1.3 Key Terminology

To effectively communicate this mid-stage exploitation of Urban ReLeaf, it is first important to clarify and align the key terminology used in this report with that of the European Commission (EC).

In this report, **results** refer to “any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights”. (EC, 2024, pg. 31).

Exploitation refers to the “use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a

product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities” (EC, 2024, pg. 31).

This deliverable does not focus on all the results produced by Urban ReLeaf, but instead on a smaller number of **KERs** which are defined as *tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature’ which have been deemed to be of high priority for project transfer actions”*. Simply put, these are the key results which have high potential to create lasting impact through the Urban ReLeaf partners or other stakeholders.

Impact is a core concept within exploitation. Horizon Europe (the co-funder of Urban ReLeaf) defines three types of impact tracked through key pathways (EU, 2021):

Scientific Impact:

- Creating high-quality new knowledge.
- Strengthening human capital in R&I.
- Fostering diffusion of knowledge and open science.

Societal Impact:

- Addressing EU policy priorities & global challenges through R&I.
- Delivering benefits & impacts via R&I missions.
- Strengthening the uptake of R&I in society.

Economic Impact:

- Generating innovation-based growth.
- Creating more and better jobs.
- Leveraging investment in R&I.

Exploitation is the key link between the results produced and achieving impact. As highlighted in the introductory section exploitation and impact are cross-cutting themes amongst all work packages and associated deliverables.

1.4 Document Structure

The report begins by introducing the purpose of the deliverable, key terminology, and its relevance within the broader project framework (section 1). This is followed by an overview of Urban ReLeaf’s approach to exploitation, which outlines the project’s strategy for maximising the impact of its results through various exploitation pathways, including commercial, policy, and non-commercial applications (section 2). This is followed by the methodology and activities used to inform exploitation since the projects inception, including the value proposition workshops for co-production and results (section 3).

The core of this deliverable is an overview of the KERs, target stakeholders, current readiness levels, and exploitation measures, anticipated outcomes and impact. This is complemented by a summary of cross-cutting exploitation opportunities and categorisation into policy, commercial and non-commercial exploitation (section 4). The report concludes by presenting the plan for the next steps for further developing exploitation, including plans for intellectual property rights management, workshops, and integration into EU dissemination platforms (section 5).

2 Urban ReLeaf's approach to exploitation

Urban ReLeaf employs a multi-faceted exploitation approach to maximise the impact of its results across different exploitation pathways. As exploitation is a shared responsibility among all project partners, it follows co-production approaches and methodologies (Norström et al, 2020; Follett & Marra, 2016). There are a diversity of results necessitating approaches that go beyond commercial exploitation. To do this Urban ReLeaf has adopted a *value proposition* method (Žlender & Šuklje, 2023; Strategyzer, 2025) which recognises commercial, non-commercial and policy exploitation and their relevant stakeholder beneficiaries.

As detailed in the Urban ReLeaf - Periodic Technical Report Part B 1.2, the project is on track to produce a variety of tangible outputs including the Urban ReLeaf Toolkit and Roadmap, wearable sensors for environmental monitoring, citizen science applications, high-resolution green elements for urban planning, governance models, and impact evaluation datasets. The Urban ReLeaf proposal identified KERs and target beneficiaries including scientific communities, citizen science networks, policymakers, local government, environmental NGOs, community groups, and the general public. More specifically, it highlights:

- **Citizens Engagement:** through "Community and Culture Pop-up Labs", Insights Workshops, citizen science participation through city campaigns and uptake of citizen generated results.
- **Policy Makers & Local Governments:** Dissemination via impact briefs, governance models, and integration of project activities into local policies.
- **Scientific Community:** Engagement through workshops, conference presentations, publications, and collaboration
- **Future Practitioners:** An accelerator programme will explore opportunities and barriers to broader implementation and scalability.

Additionally, the approach to established exploitation includes a range of cross-cutting exploitation activities (WP5 & WP6):

- A Community of Practice (CoP) to ensure knowledge sharing and stakeholder engagement.
- Strategic use of partner networks and an expert advisory board for broader dissemination.
- Dissemination via policy-relevant online platforms such as the ICLEI city network, the Green City Accord, and the Smart Cities EU SCALE platform.
- Business-oriented pathways, including Design for Business (DfB) Sprints and cost-benefit analysis to inform commercialization.

These exploitation activities will create tangible pathways to impact including:

- Greater citizen participation in environmental monitoring.

- Expanded availability and integration of citizen-generated data into official observation systems (e.g., Copernicus, GEOSS).
- Development of toolkits and methodologies for environmental data collection.
- Deployment of low-cost wearable environmental sensors across pilot cities.
- Contributions to innovative governance models and EU Green Deal objectives.

At this mid-point it is useful to revise the initial plan and further develop the exploitation activities and measures in line with the strategic opportunities which emerged since the inception of Urban ReLeaf.

3 Methodology and activities to inform exploitation

The exploitation plan has been developed from several co-production activities with the consortium partners. This included two in-person exploitation workshops, using a value proposition methodology, a co-produced results register aiding the prioritisation of KERs, and follow-up bilateral communication with individual partners to further develop the plan for exploitation. An overview of the approach and methods is also shown below in Figure 2.

Figure 2 is split into two phases of exploitation, with phase 1 outlining the activities and measures to date (Feb 2025), and phase 2, the plans for further developing exploitation in Urban ReLeaf. Phase 1 of Figure 2 begins with the process of distilling the expected knowledge produced by Urban ReLeaf into a prioritised set of KERs established through a co-produced results register and prioritisation activity. Co-design methodologies and activities described in sections 3.1-3.3 further refined the exploitation approach to establish the (1) target users, (2) exploitation measures and activities, (3) anticipated outcomes and (4) potential impact. Moving into phase 2 of Figure 2, a series of additional co-design activities will take place, as described later in section 5 of the report. Collectively these feed into a final exploitation plan for Urban ReLeaf at the end of the project (M48).

Figure 2: Overview of Urban ReLeaf approach to exploitation and methods used

3.1 Exploitation Workshop 1 – General Assembly in Utrecht, The Netherlands, April 2024

The first exploitation workshop was held in-person at the 2024 Urban ReLeaf General Assembly in Utrecht, The Netherlands (

Figure 3). The aim of this initial session was to highlight Urban ReLeaf’s approach to exploitation and introduce exploitation more generally, including key methods. This collaborative workshop also sought to highlight the key areas partners considered important for sustaining activity and ensuring long-term commitment and collaboration by answering the following foundational questions:

- 1) What do you need to sustain activity?

- 2) Who do you need to talk to in your organisation and externally?
- 3) What is your organisational commitment to sustaining activity?

Through the participatory co-design workshop, stakeholders engaged in a collaborative mapping and ideation exercise to surface and explore exploitation directions for the project. This generative session - which served both to raise awareness and spark discussion - led to the clustering of preliminary ideas around three thematic areas: sustaining citizen science activity, strengthening stakeholder collaboration, and supporting organisational commitments.

Figure 3: Workshop - Urban ReLeaf GA, 2024

The emerging concepts, which should be viewed as conversation starters rather than definitive solutions, included preliminary thinking around:

- A Citizen Science Toolkit that could potentially support guidance, data sharing, and practice sharing.
- Initial sketches of governance models and stakeholder frameworks to explore roles and responsibilities.
- Early conceptual work on approaches for policy integration and monitoring systems that might help embed citizen data into decision-making.
- Preliminary discussions around inclusive participation guidelines and technology reliability considerations.

These workshop outputs represent the first steps in the dialogue around exploitation, inviting further refinement and discussion with stakeholders as ideas mature and evolve.

3.2 Co-produced Results Register

Prior to the second exploitation workshop, an online results register was created and shared with all partners to collate current and expected results from Urban ReLeaf, including those additional to the original proposal. Partners populated an editable spreadsheet, as illustrated in Table 1, reporting (1) The organisation, work package/ task/ deliverable the result is from, (2) name and description of result, (3) indicate its technology readiness level (TRL); (4) keyword, (5) target audience/ stakeholder, (6) primary categorisation of the result; (7) an optional secondary categorisation; and (8) if this is a priority output/result for exploitation. This initial stage allowed partners to enter all results with exploitation potential, providing a foundation for identifying the KERs. Some sections were left incomplete which identified an “exploitation knowledge gap”, this was subsequently addressed in Exploitation Workshop 2. A completed version of the co-produced result register can be found in Appendix 2.

Table 1: Urban ReLeaf Results Register Headings

Source / achieved via	Result: Name & Description (sample possible results & planned)	Technology readiness levels (TRL) (select most appropriate from list)	Target Audience (s)/ Stakeholder (s)	Primary Result Category (select most appropriate from list)	Secondary Result Category (select most appropriate from list) <i>Optional</i>	Current use/ impacts (if applicable/known)	Priority Output/ Result?
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3.3 Exploitation Workshop 2 – General Assembly Cascais, Portugal, January 2025

Following the co-production of the results register an in-person interactive workshop was held at the 2025 Urban ReLeaf General Assembly in Cascais, Portugal (Figure 4). The aims of the workshop were to:

- Identify KERs/outputs.
- Identify new and existing exploitation and impact pathways, including commercialisation, non-commercialisation, policy impact and broader value creation.
- Support the co-production of the Urban ReLeaf results register.
- Develop collective understanding around exploitation.

The workshop commenced with an initial introductory talk which outlined the aims, purpose and structure of the workshop, as well as clarity on key terminology such as results, exploitation and KER to allow everyone to develop a common understanding. For the activity, project partners were purposively mixed into groups to integrate different partner organisations, forming seven total groups, with a self-nominated note taker and presenter for each group.

The first task was for each group to review the pre-populated results register and each select 1-2 priority or KER which they were familiar with. These KERs formed the focus

of the activity. Using a bespoke canvas (Appendix 1) the groups worked together to answer six questions designed to stimulate and co-develop exploitation pathways:

- Who could use this? (relevant stakeholders and end users)
- What problems does it solve? (what is the added value)
- Are there any key policy hooks? (policies, programmes or strategies)
- What would they need to start/further use it? (resources, further testing)
- If/how can this be scaled and replicated? (protocol, input from other partners)
- Who else needs to be involved to exploit this result? (other partners, stakeholder)

Two moderators leading WP6 moved between groups to steer them to think practically and focused on identifying actionable and tangible steps to exploit their selected KER(s). Each group was then asked to share their discussion with the full group of partners, including the top result with the highest exploitation potential, a key policy hook or impact pathway to exploitation, three specific steps needed to move it forward and whether they needed any help from other partners. This then led to a plenary discussion focused on shared opportunities and further resources needed, with the discussion recorded by a note-taker on a bespoke canvas to consolidate the key workshop findings.

The results of the workshop (the activity and plenary canvases) were then analysed using simple thematic mapping and inductive content analysis (Given, 2008) to identify key pathways and overlaps between KER. The results of which are presented in section 4 and fed into Table 2.

Figure 4: Urban ReLeaf partners engaging in the exploitation workshop at the Urban ReLeaf General Assembly, using the value proposition canvas.

To solidify the key knowledge generated in the interactive workshop several follow up meetings and bilateral communications were conducted with result leads. These focused on filling gaps and agreeing specific pathways and steps to exploitation.

4 Key Exploitable Results: outreach, impact and exploitation pathways

4.1 Key Exploitable Results

As outlined in the Urban ReLeaf Technical Report (Part B) for the first period of the project Urban ReLeaf is making good progress in meeting its objectives and work undertaking. As part of that report, the KERs from the project are identified and their exploitation measures further developed. The previously identified KERs, the results register (Appendix 2), and co-creation activities were further used to identify additional KERs and develop exploitation pathways to achieve project impact. Table 2, outlines and summarises the KERs identified at this project mid-stage, exploitation measures, target stakeholders, readiness¹, anticipated outcomes and impacts of these results. Together these form a value proposition for each KER – the unique value and innovation of each of these results. As part of this, Table 2 maps the target stakeholders initially outlined in D6.1, to specific KERs.

¹ During the creation of the results register (3.2) TRL was used to establish readiness level. Going through this process and the subsequent workshop (3.3) revealed a more holistic readiness classification was needed to capture more qualitative results. To produce D6.6 (Urban ReLeaf outreach, impact and exploitation report II), the use other standardised readiness levels will be explored.

Table 2: Urban ReLeaf Key Exploitable Results and Measures

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
<i>What will be or has been generated?</i>	<i>What are the specific needs or gaps this result addresses?</i>	<i>What stage of development is the result in for exploitation?</i>	<i>Who will use or further update the result and who will benefit from it?</i>	<i>What exploitation measures will take place?</i>	<i>What changes have happened/ are expected to happen as a result of the exploitation?</i>	<i>What are the expected wider scientific, economic, and societal impacts?</i>
<p>Strategy blueprints for Inclusive Citizen Science (D2.2)</p> <p>VUB</p>	Addressing epistemic injustice in CS data collection and a lack of inclusive methodologies and guidance.	Proof-of-concept	Local & regional policymakers, CS coordinators, CS platforms, higher education institutions, educational organisations.	<p>Validation in pilot cities and accelerator programme to refine blueprint and produce case studies.</p> <p>Promotion through posters, infographics, presentation at events (academic and policy).</p> <p>Explore development of an “inclusivity tracker” monitoring dashboard as a future service offering” (e.g., in future projects), including possibility of open source, with commercialisation via research support. – this will be explored further through Business for Design sprints.</p> <p>Academic paper on inclusive CS.</p>	More equitable and inclusive designing and recruitment in CS campaigns, including better monitoring and protocols.	<p>Greater Inclusion of knowledge and needs of genuinely vulnerable groups in decision making → Improved scientific understanding of various phenomenon due to more comprehensive and complete datasets → better informed and fairer decision-making at policy levels</p> <p>Contributions to SDG challenge “leaving no one behind</p>

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
<p>Best Practices for Inclusive Culture and Community Pop-Up Labs (D2.3)</p> <p>UNIVDUN</p>	<p>Lack methodological maturity for inclusive, community-driven citizen science engagement and data insights.</p>	<p>Basic validation in a relevant environment</p>	<p>Community organisations, research/academic institutions, policymakers.</p>	<p>Expansion of pop-up lab models and arts-based research methods.</p> <p>Engagement of creative data-driven outputs to new audiences.</p> <p>Science/policy practice dissemination events.</p> <p>Academic paper <i>in Humanities & Social Sciences Communications</i> or <i>Citizen Science Theory and Practice</i>.</p>	<p>Methodological advancement, including more vulnerable groups in engaging with the data and decision making through use of inclusive community pop-up labs in CS.</p>	<p>More inclusive CS data.</p>
<p>Tree Canopy Map (D3.4, 3.8)</p> <p>CLS</p>	<p>There is currently an absence of very high-resolution green elements in European cities</p> <p>Requiring an improved method and higher resolution data on urban trees in European cities.</p>	<p>Technology prototype in an operational environment</p>	<p>Policy makers, Copernicus teams, urban planners, greenspace planners.</p>	<p>Integration with Copernicus programmes and products.</p> <p>Connecting to other relevant datasets and navigate copyright to allow open access.</p> <p>Communication on the availability of the data and connecting with possible end-users.</p> <p>Further development of the dataset though other projects, including further funding to exploring commercialisation</p>	<p>Finer and more detailed dataset of city tree canopy for European cities beyond the pilot cities.</p> <p>Improved Copernicus Urban Atlas products.</p>	<p>Evidence-based policymaking in European cities.</p> <p>Improved Copernicus-based urban greenspace monitoring for the EU Green Deal.</p>

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
				opportunities including developing marketing approaches. – will explore further through Business for Design sprint.		
Participatory Tree Register Application (D3.5) CIBOS	<p>Lack of active sampling application to support individual tree mapping in cities, including species, conditions and relevant attribute.</p> <p>Existing tree registry data in most cities is often incomplete/ outdated.</p>	Technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment.	Municipalities, environmental agencies and NGOs, urban planning or greening departments, Research Institutes.	<p>Additional features for city uptake - integration with "reimbursement" strategies, e.g. collection of virtual coins and consuming them in municipality services, such as parking, charging, etc.</p> <p>Open data alignment and integration with other data stream e.g. cadastre data, UrbanAtlas, drone flights data.</p> <p>Explore licensing opportunities in partnership with a municipality, environmental agency etc. – will explore further through Business for Design sprint.</p> <p>Planned Publications.</p>	<p>More detailed urban tree datasets for European cities at the individual tree level.</p> <p>Streamlined monitoring processes and tools.</p> <p>Better management of tasks for tree-related activities for the personnel of the greening departments.</p>	<p>Use of CS data in urban climate protection and adaption measures.</p> <p>Future and increased tree planting.</p>
Urban ReLeaf Perceptions Application (D3.5) IIASA	Lack of active sampling applications based on user technology to collect citizens'	Technology prototype in a relevant environment.	Citizens, Public Authorities, Research Institutes, CSOs.	<p>Protocol and guidelines to use the app.</p> <p>Urban ReLeaf accelerator programme and toolkit.</p>	Customized geolocated survey app for citizen engagement being used in other locations (cities,	Long-term inclusion of citizen observations into authoritative data streams relating

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
	in-situ perceptions of urban spaces.			Journal publication. Integration in suite of Geo-Wiki tools.	towns, natural parks etc.) beyond the project.	to, amongst others, people's perceptions of greenspaces via flexible and adaptable tools.
TRH Sensors & EcoPulse Mobile Application/ web platform (D3.6) ICCS	Need for low-cost lightweight digital tool that will enable the collection of geo-localised measurements of temperature and relative humidity and well as subjective perceptions over heat stress. Overcome operational and maintenance costs required for the deployment of traditional sensors network. Provision of a self-protection system with personalised alerts during overheating episodes.	Technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Citizens (B2C), Public Authorities, Research Institutes, Health Agencies, Health Insurance Companies (B2G, B2B).	Protocol and guidelines targeted at stakeholders to increase chances of uptake. Further development and testing the whole digital solution. Increase user experience. Refinement of data visualisation in the Web Platform. Explore alternative funding schemes to support the commercialisation roadmap of this technology (e.g., Horizon Results Booster, Dealflow.eu and the Enterprise Europe Network - — will explore further through Business for Design sprint. Presentations at conferences, and possible publications.	Enhanced real-time urban climate monitoring across more European cities. Identification of hotspots and "coolspots" may lead to a more efficient sustainable planning.	Long-term inclusion of citizen observations into authoritative data streams. Increase resilience of neighbourhoods in relation to heat stress, planning, design of NbS Self-awareness and self-protection of marginalised and heat-vulnerable social groups.

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
<p>Guidelines for QA/QC in Citizen Science Data (D3.7)</p> <p>ICCS</p>	<p>Need for established methodological framework that will ensure citizen-generated data meets data quality standards to enable integrated with the professional measurements and uptake by cities.</p>	<p>Under development</p>	<p>CS technology users, research institutions, local authorities, ICT and AI companies.</p>	<p>CoP – to communicate and disseminate the guidelines.</p> <p>Dissemination via EU CS networks, sister projects and wider networks.</p>	<p>Practical methods for CS data quality assessment and reporting.</p> <p>Data Evaluation based on DQ elements of INSPIRE Directive.</p>	<p>Facilitates data integration into official EU platforms.</p> <p>Improved quality of CS data being produced.</p> <p>Improved credibility & interoperability of citizen science data.</p>
<p>Evaluation/Impact Framework & Impact Briefs (D4.10)</p> <p>IIASA</p>	<p>Need for robust citizen science impact assessment tools of CS pilots, with a focus on impacts on policy.</p>	<p>Under development</p>	<p>Policymakers, researchers, funding agencies.</p>	<p>Dissemination in Horizon Europe networks and relevant conferences.</p> <p>Journal publication.</p> <p>Urban ReLeaf accelerator programme and toolkit.</p>	<p>Improved evaluation frameworks and assessment methodology to establish impact of CS with transferability to other projects.</p> <p>Insights and recommendations on operationalising CS in urban greenspace planning.</p>	<p>Improved transparency and understanding of the impacts of using CS for city urban greening/ environmental projects. Further improvement and development of IA tools in CS.</p>
<p>Innovative Governance Models for Pilot Cities (D5.2)</p>	<p>Pervasive governance barriers exist in European cities to effectively</p>	<p>Proof-of-concept</p>	<p>Local and EU policymakers, urban planners, municipalities.</p>	<p>Testing transferability, including through the accelerator programme.</p>	<p>Greater uptake and transferability of the governance models beyond Urban ReLeaf.</p>	<p>Scalable and more receptive citizen participation governance</p>

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
ICLEI	incorporate citizen science in environmental decision making requiring scalable and transferable governance models.			<p>Dissemination and knowledge exchange with EU initiatives and partners.</p> <p>CoP – A key exploitation activity to connect results with potential end users, supported by policy briefs and published through ICLEI channels (e.g., e-library, dissemination via Newsletters, etc.).</p> <p>Policy recommendation document, presented at relevant events such as EURESFO, ESCT Conference, ECCA, or similar.</p>	Cities more effectively navigating barriers to CS uptake.	<p>models across European cities.</p> <p>Increased trust and improved confidence of governance actors in citizen observations.</p>
Urban ReLeaf Toolkit (D5.3) VUB	Need for structured toolkit to support the adoption of citizen science methodologies in urban governance.	Concept & application stage.	Municipal authorities, CSOs, CS practitioners and researchers, higher education institutions, educational organisations.	<p>Deployment (test & refinement) in accelerator programme.</p> <p>Dissemination via EU networks, sister projects and wider networks.</p> <p>Presenting at EU events and other relevant academic venues.</p> <p>Toolkit produced in an engaging and intuitive format for target users through co-creation.</p>	More cities developing and using data-driven and citizen-powered urban greenspace monitoring approaches.	<p>Increased uptake of citizen science data sets in city policies and decision making.</p> <p>Urban greening decisions which are more inclusive of the communities they target.</p> <p>Systematic integration of</p>

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
						<p>citizen data in EU urban policies.</p> <p>Policy reflects citizens interest.</p>
<p>Urban ReLeaf Adoption Roadmap (D5.3)</p> <p>IIASA</p>	<p>Strategic vision and plan outlining future pathways for citizen science and data uptake for public policy</p>	<p>Under development</p>	<p>Policymakers, researchers, citizen science practitioners, funding agencies.</p>	<p>Dissemination in Horizon Europe networks and relevant conferences.</p> <p>Journal publication.</p> <p>Urban ReLeaf accelerator programme.</p>	<p>Better informed policy and planning processes on the integration of citizen science.</p> <p>Direction setting for future research.</p>	<p>Future funding calls supporting and aligned with the pathways and needs outlined in the roadmap.</p> <p>Citizen science being formally embedded in policy making processes.</p>
<p>Storytelling Strategy & Framework (D6.1)</p> <p>UNIVDUN</p>	<p>Novel approach to engaging narratives to support citizen and other stakeholder engagement.</p>	<p>Basic principles observed and reported.</p>	<p>General public, policymakers, research community, professional project teams.</p>	<p>Multimedia content, storytelling workshops to raise awareness of this approach.</p> <p>Methodology and Framework for storytelling.</p> <p>Strategy and guidance for storytelling for different stakeholder groups e.g. citizens, policy-makers.</p> <p>Possibly part of the Urban ReLeaf Toolkit.</p>	<p>More creative approaches to engaging diverse communities and communicating CS results.</p>	<p>Broader uptake of CS activities.</p>

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
<p>Design for Business: Tools & Methods (D6.7)</p> <p>UNIVDUN</p>	<p>Need for sustainable commercialisation of project outcomes and methods to support it.</p>	<p>Early-stage development</p>	<p>Start-ups, innovation hubs, EU funding bodies, consultancy practices, professional bodies.</p>	<p>Explore options to produce transferable canvas/tools to support research exploitation.</p>	<p>Adoption of Urban ReLeaf tools beyond the project.</p>	<p>Long-term economic viability, private-sector adoption, further innovation.</p>
<p>Air Quality Data Streams:</p> <p>NOA</p> <p>Riga</p> <p>Athens</p> <p>Dundee</p>	<p>Need to test assumptions of greening and air quality at the local scale for vulnerable communities.</p>	<p>Technology prototype in an operational environment</p>	<p>Citizens, transport planners, health agencies, policy Makers, greenspace planners, academic/research institutes.</p>	<p>Integration with city data platforms</p> <p>Data visualisation platform so that citizens can see the results in an easy to digest format.</p> <p>Expanding to other locations to increase knowledge base.</p> <p>Engage with key stakeholders within local authorities to demonstrate the datasets.</p> <p>Riga: Monitoring for low emission zone implementation; engagement and dissemination with housing and environmental department to uptake sensor data i.e. central heating planning.</p>	<p>Improved air quality awareness and action at the local scale.</p> <p>Improved targeting of planting locations for NbS and Green Infrastructure to improve air quality.</p> <p>Riga: Riga City Air Quality Improvement Action Programme for 2026-2030; Smart City Guidelines.</p> <p>Dundee: Integration into Air Quality Strategy.</p>	<p>Improved decision making and planning in terms of green elements in European cities.</p> <p>Supports EU environmental and public health goals.</p>

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
				<p>Athens: Not established at this point.</p> <p>Dundee: Not established at this point.</p>		
<p>Greenspace Perceptions Dataset</p> <p>IIASA</p> <p>Dundee</p> <p>Cascais</p>	Data gap as to how citizens, and especially hard-to-reach citizens use and perceive their cities greenspaces.	Technology prototype in an operational environment	Policy makers (national & city), urban planners, greenspace managers and communities themselves.	<p>Cross-cutting: Open data APIs, effective data visualisation, policy integration through presenting data to different departments within the local authorities.</p> <p>Cascais: Publicising the results to the community on social media. Direct engagement with Urban Planning Department, the Green Spaces Department and the Environment and Sea Department to share the data.</p> <p>Dundee: Input across council including to the Local Development Planning 2027 process evidence base; Open Space Strategy; Potential funding applications with groups implementing identified wants from the community.</p>	<p>Integration of the data to inform specific decisions, greenspace strategies, plans and policies</p> <p>Case studies for wider replication</p> <p>Cascais: Inform the Green Space and Tree Protection Regulation and Good Practice Manual “Renatura”</p> <p>Dundee: Informing Plans: Open space Strategy; Local Development; Climate Action; Net Zero; Sustainable Transport Delivery; Local Place; Biodiversity Actions;</p>	<p>CS elements and evidence integrated in public policy and urban planning process.</p> <p>Increased acceptance of CS data from authoritative points of view.</p> <p>CS data is accessible within public body data ecosystems.</p>

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
<p>Participatory Tree Data Streams (Mannheim & Athens)</p> <p>CIBOS</p> <p>Mannheim Athens</p>	<p>Lack of individual tree level data for cities to provide planners, policy makers, managers etc with insight into current status of greenspace/tree coverage.</p>	<p>Technology prototype in an operational environment</p>	<p>Municipalities, greenspace planners and managers.</p> <p>Citizens who can contribute and expand their knowledge of urban trees to understand protection and preservation of urban greenery as a communal task.</p>	<p>Engage with key stakeholders within local authorities to demonstrate the datasets.</p> <p>Mannheim: Establishment of a new server to link the data from the municipal tree registry with the new data collected.</p> <p>Athens: Exploit the trees management platform of the city. Provide know-how and knowledge sharing to other Greek cities on trees registries.</p>	<p>Enhanced urban tree management and planning, especially in hard-to-reach communities.</p> <p>Comprehensive tree registry as a basis for planning.</p>	<p>Long-term inclusion of citizen observations into authoritative data streams.</p>
<p>Temperature Relative Humidity (TRH) Data Streams</p> <p>CIBOS</p> <p>IIASA</p> <p>Utrecht Athens Riga Dundee Cascais</p>	<p>Lack of hyper-localised and inclusive citizen experience urban heat data for climate resilience planning.</p> <p>Citizen insights are needed to make neighbourhoods more climate resilient.</p>	<p>Technology prototype in an operational environment</p>	<p>Municipalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Planning -Public Health -Greenspace team -Climate & Sustainability <p>Constructions companies and urban developers.</p> <p>National metrological institutes.</p> <p>Public Health institutes.</p>	<p>Cross-cutting: Engage with key stakeholders within local authorities to demonstrate the datasets.</p> <p>Data visualisation: both bespoke platforms and integration with city portals.</p> <p>Data validation for heat stress modelling.</p> <p>Staff training and capacity building to use and integrate.</p>	<p>Integration of the data to inform specific decisions, greenspace strategies, plans and policies.</p> <p>Riga: Riga Urban Greening Plan for 2027–2031; Riga Action Programme; Smart City Guidelines.</p> <p>Cascais: Inform the Green Space and Tree</p>	<p>CS elements and evidence integrated in public policy and urban planning process.</p> <p>Increased acceptance of CS data from authoritative point of view.</p> <p>Resilience to heat stress in the vulnerable areas in the pilot cities</p>

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
			Community associations.	<p>Utrecht: Demonstrations and workshops with policy colleagues; sharing insights within organisation.</p> <p>Athens: Not established yet</p> <p>Riga: Data and information exchange with other projects/departments in the municipality related to heat islands (Life Latest Adapt, Satsdifaction, MultiClimact); Prioritization of problem spaces in Riga greening plan</p> <p>Dundee: Use data to support implementation of heat island management interventions.</p> <p>Cascais: Creation of a thermal comfort map of urban green spaces; Visits to urban green spaces to awareness the community to the issue of thermal comfort; Publicising the results on social networks and municipal platforms. Direct engagement with urban planning</p>	<p>Protection Regulation and Good Practice Manual "Renatura". Informing the design of "cooler" routes for the elderly when traveling to the services such as pharmacies.</p> <p>Dundee: Water Resilient Dundee Air Quality Strategy (heat islands have poorer air quality) Biodiversity Action Plan Open space Strategy; Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment 2024.</p> <p>Utrecht: Support decision making related to: Climate adaptation implementation programme; The Biodiversity-approach in Town</p>	through targeted urban greening.

Key Exploitable Results	Specific Needs/Gap Addressing	Current Readiness Level	Target Groups (s)	Exploitation Measures & Activities	Anticipated Outcomes	Potential Impact
				department, the green spaces department and the environment and sea department to share the data.	and Village; Healthy Urban Living for Everyone; Spatial policy: Spatial Strategy Utrecht 2040. Athens: 100 Neutral, Cities, Net Zero Cities, Climate City Contracts.	

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Table 2 provides a comprehensive overview of the individual KERs identified at this mid-stage, focusing on different forms of exploitation. Importantly, many of the exploitation activities and measures are indicative, showing the anticipated exploitation plan, opposed to definitive actions. Over the remaining project period these exploitation measures will be solidified further through the activities outlined later in section 5 of this report. The following sub-sections highlights and summarises the different types of exploitation the partners will target.

4.1.1 Crosscutting exploitation opportunities

There are several crosscutting opportunities for exploitation which traverse individual KERs. These include:

- Testimonials from result users to market and promote the results for exploitation.
- Strong narratives around the results to engage potential end users.
- The importance of the pilots as key exploitation pathways for other results by formulating success stories and validation to other cities through case studies.
- The need for data sets to be equally robust for science, innovation and policy goals.
- Utilising the strong Urban ReLeaf brand and (social media) communication channels to support exploitation of key results.

The consortium of partners also identified cross-cutting exploitation priorities for the remainder of the project which can strengthen the exploitation potential of the results produced from Urban ReLeaf. These include the need for:

- Uptake by the accelerator cities to validate and demonstrate transferability of the KERs to other European cities.
- Dissemination of KERs through the WP5 CoP working groups to facilitate peer learning among cities and stakeholders.
- Development of engaging and standardised data visualisation for maximum benefit in city pilots and for adaptive scalability of the Urban ReLeaf approach.
- Engagement of other relevant departments (not directly involved with Urban ReLeaf) within local authorities/municipalities to break down silo working and exploit datasets and new knowledge across organisations.
- Phased timeline for KERs to maximize exploitation opportunities as part of the development cycle.
- Strengthened connection with Urban ReLeaf sister projects as key result users.

- Ongoing monitoring of exploitation of results to share successes, progress and additional resources as needed.
- Explore joint funding opportunities to build on the results created in Urban ReLeaf.

4.1.2 Policy Exploitation

One of the key areas of exploitation for Urban ReLeaf is through the incorporation of results in public policies, urban plans, programmes and strategies ranging from local to national. Specific policy exploitation pathways relate to the individual data streams outlined in Table 2. Figure 5 summarises the range of policy and planning documents which the city partners will target for exploitation.

Figure 5: Identified Urban ReLeaf exploitation pathways for policy impact.

In addition, policy exploitation will be targeted through:

- Policy briefs and recommendations presented at relevant events (e.g., EURESFO, ESCT Conference, ECCA).
- Dissemination of key results through EU networks and initiatives.
- Integration of datasets into city portals and cross-departmental policy applications within municipalities.
- Collaboration with environmental agencies and municipalities to align open data strategies with policy frameworks.

4.1.3 Commercial Exploitation

Several KERs have been identified as having potential for commercial exploitation. A key priority is to explore these commercialisation options further, including using the Design for Business methodology. At this mid-stage commercial exploitation will be explored further including:

- TRH Sensors and EcoPulse platform through exploring additional funding schemes.
- Exploration of licensing opportunities for the Participatory Tree Register Application in partnership with municipalities.
- Development of an “Inclusivity Tracker” as a potential commercial service offering.
- Further funding and business model development for the Tree Canopy Map to explore commercialisation opportunities.
- Testing and refinement of digital tools and applications to enhance user experience and potential market adoption.

4.1.4 Non-Commercial Exploitation

Academic, research and citizen science stakeholders will primarily be targeted through non-commercial exploitation activities. These include:

- Academic publications and dissemination through journals and conferences.
- Expansion of best practices guidelines for pop-up community labs and creative data-driven research outputs.
- Training and capacity building for local authorities and research partners to facilitate knowledge transfer.
- Public engagement strategies, including storytelling workshops and multimedia campaigns.
- Integration of tools and methodologies into research projects and accelerator programmes to refine and improve applications.

5 Next steps: further developing exploitation

This section provides an outline and overview of planned activities and methods to further develop the exploitation planning in phase 2 as visualised in Figure 6. This includes key next steps to address Intellectual Property Rights, ownership, use of business model canvas and ongoing exploitation monitoring. The results of these activities will inform D6.6 Exploitation Plan 2, delivered at the end of the Urban ReLeaf project (M48).

Figure 6: Indicative timeline for phase 2 of exploitation planning.

5.1 Intellectual property rights, ownership and acknowledgement (M30-M31, M40-M42)

Intellectual Property (IP) refers to creations of the mind, such as ideas, inventions, or processes, that are legally recognised as a form of property. IP plays a crucial role in determining the rights associated with the use and commercialisation of KERs. The Consortium Agreement (CA) establishes guidelines regarding ownership, including joint ownership when results are developed collaboratively by multiple partners. Additionally, the CA outlines the procedures for transferring ownership rights. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) regulates how IP can be used. Through IP protection, the owner can achieve a competitive advantage. Examples of protection are trademarks, copyrights and patents.

The Urban ReLeaf proposal outlined that *“the foreground IPR from Urban ReLeaf will be shared jointly by those producing the outputs, the majority of which will have non-commercial value, e.g., the Urban ReLeaf Toolkit, the adaptive governance models, and Roadmap etc. and be openly available using a Creative Commons attribution license to be agreed. If other outputs may potentially generate income, the Urban ReLeaf GA will outline the foreground IPR arrangements for these different outputs. A dedicated IPR consultant will assist partners in the management of IPR protection measures. To facilitate innovation actions from the start, the consortium will initiate appropriate IPR management steps and foreground IPR discussions and subsequent agreements as part of the exploitation activities in WP6”*. A key next step for phase 2 of the exploitation planning is to establish and define the ownership and intellectual property rights related to the identified KERs through a pragmatic and operational approach, outlined in the steps below. Drawing from experience in previous projects (e.g., LandSense, GROW Observatory, WeObserve), this plan will build on the provisions agreed to in both the Grant Agreement (GA) and CA for Urban ReLeaf.

Outputs generated during the project are often built upon components brought by partners to the project. These are explicitly identified in the CA.

Step 1: IPR presentation – the University of Dundee will lead an IPR session with the consortium, featuring in-house legal IP expertise. This workshop will indicatively take place between M30-M32. The aims of the workshop will be to (1) explain licensing e.g. creative commons (CC), acknowledgements, ownership, and IPR for a sub-set of relevant results, including the roles and rights of consortium members; (2) establish the ownership of specific KERs; and (3) where relevant, identify necessary IP Protection Strategies.

Step 2: Ownership and acknowledgements – Following on from the workshop a results ownership list will be developed to be included in D6.6 (Exploitation Report II). This will establish:

- Single or joint ownership of results.
- Background IP.
- Result owner(s).
- Results acknowledgement(s)
- If the owners exploit the result.
- In which form will the results be made available to other consortium members and/or third parties.
- If the exploitation of the results require access to background of one or several consortium members.
- If the exploitation of the results require access to third party IPR.
- If a joint ownership agreement is required.

Step 3: IP protection and licencing - To ensure IP protection for some Key Exploitable Results (KER), especially those with commercial exploitation potential, a proprietary license may be needed.

At this stage, the following KERs may require custom IP protection:

- 1) TRH Sensors & EcoPulse Mobile Application
- 2) Participatory Tree Registry Application
- 3) Urban ReLeaf Cities Application for Perceptions Mapping
- 4) Tree Canopy Layers

For joint owned results the obligations and responsibilities for exploitation will be established between partners.

5.2 Design for business sprints (M33-M35)

The *Design for Business* model developed by the University of Dundee and the V&A Dundee will be applied between M22-M35 of the project as a key activity to refine and further develop the exploitation plan with the consortium. This will be an online session focused on further developing priority results for commercialisation and non-commercialisation.

Design for Business is a proven innovation approach which encourages innovation in businesses by demonstrating the role design thinking can play in unlocking “non-design” problems, including business challenges and identifying and exploiting new opportunities (Follett & Marra, 2016; Woods et al., 2015; Coulson & Woods, 2016). It does this by thinking about new approaches in business, leading to new ways of working that improve and enhance how products, processes and services are conceived, developed, tested, marketed, and used.

At the heart of the design for business approach are five key design principles:

- To **question** – is the right challenge being addressed?
- To **be user-centered** – what does the user gain from the problem being solved?
- To **communicate** creatively and visually, making the story clear and relevant in the design process.
- To **collaborate** – teamwork with stakeholders enhances outcomes.
- To **iterate** – “make, test and learn” early and often to cut risk.

Drawing from the design for business approach a bespoke online canvas will be created in Miro for the online sprints based on previously developed templates (Appendix 3). These will build on the value proposition methods developed and applied to date.

5.3 Exploitation Workshop 3 – 2026 Urban ReLeaf General Assembly (M37-M40)

A final exploitation workshop will be held at the 2026 Urban ReLeaf General Assembly. This will build on the Design for Business sprints and aim to finalise the plan for exploitation post-project. Given the latter stage of the project, a proportion of the time will be spent on evaluating risks for exploitation. The outline/plan of this workshop is purposively open to be able to respond to key priorities which emerge.

5.4 Horizon Results Platform and Booster (M44-M46)

In the next phase, the project will explore the opportunities available from the Horizon Results Platform and Horizon Results Booster (HRB) service to further support exploitation, especially beyond the lifetime of the project. The Horizon Results Booster initiated by the European Commission has three services:

1. Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy
2. Business Plan Development
3. Go To Market.

Urban ReLeaf will explore which services may be of most benefit for the Urban ReLeaf KERs, following phase 2 of the exploitation planning.

5.5 Ongoing monitoring

To ensure the successful implementation of the exploitation plan, accurate monitoring and assessment of the exploitation actions will be carried out. This will not only allow the identification of obstacles or limitations in the exploitation process but also allow for new exploitation opportunities to be explored. Monitoring will be done through the expansion of the existing dissemination monitoring, which provides a rolling internal spreadsheet for partners to input into, with reminders sent quarterly. The following additional elements will be added to allow exploitation monitoring:

- Exploitation activities undertaken and any relevant evidence.
- Any exploitation barriers encountered.
- Which stakeholders are interested.
- Opportunities for further funding to support exploitation.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable provides a mid-term assessment of the exploitation plan for Urban ReLeaf. This includes identifying KERs, target groups, an estimation of the current readiness levels of the results, provisional exploitation measures and their anticipated outcomes and impacts. By adopting a multi-faceted exploitation strategy utilising a value proposition methodology, Urban ReLeaf has made good progress in the first half of the project in developing its plan for exploitation. By producing and identifying a diverse portfolio of KERs, Urban ReLeaf is well placed to achieve real-world impact beyond the project duration. This includes integration of this data into policymaking, and the development of low-cost environmental sensors and digital platforms with potential for policy application and commercialisation.

Going into the second half of the project, this deliverable outlines a timeline of tangible steps to further refine exploitation opportunities. Key activities include establishing intellectual property rights, utilising a Design for Business methodology, a co-design workshop and the use of the Horizon Results Booster for broader dissemination. Looking ahead, Deliverable 6.6 (due M48) will update this exploitation plan and provide updates on its progress, providing a bespoke and rigid plan for the ongoing exploitation of the results beyond the projects lifetime ensuring, replicability and scalability to achieve long-term impact.

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Appendix 1 Workshop Canvas used at the Urban ReLeaf General Assembly Cascais, Portugal

Exploitation Strategy Workshop (WP6)

Selected Key Result: (1) WP/Task (2) Name (3) Brief Description and (4) Key Partners		Why is this a key/priority result: A result with strongest potential for impact/exploitation
Who could use this? Key stakeholder/user groups	What problems does it solve? Data, knowledge methods gaps	Are there key policy hooks? Policies, programmes, regulations, strategies
Start using the result What is needed to start/further its use?	Scaled and replicated? What is needed to start/further its use?	Who else is needed? To exploit this result? Partners, stakeholders

Appendix 2 Mid-stage Urban ReLeaf results register

Source / achieved via	Result: Name & Description (sample possible results & planned)	Technology readiness levels (TRL) (select most appropriate from list)	Keyword	Target Audience(s)/ Stakeholder(s)	Primary Result Category (select most appropriate from list)	Secondary Result Category (select most appropriate from list) <i>Optional</i>	Current use/ impacts (if applicable/known)	Priority Output/ Result?
T2.1 / D2.1 (VUB)	Landscape reports: illustrates the dynamic policy landscape/processes, shows existing gaps, and offers recommendations for inclusive citizen participation and data-collection opportunities for each pilot city. Includes: one process map and one ecosystem mapping per pilot.	TRL 2: technology concept or application formulated	Tool		Knowledge & Understanding: Insight/knowledge advancement			
T2.1 / D2.1 (VUB)	Scoping review on the role of citizen science in urban greening policies and considerations for social justice	TRL 2: technology concept or application formulated	Review		Knowledge & Understanding: Insight/knowledge advancement			
T2.2 / D2.2 (VUB)	Blueprint: inclusive citizen science engagement strategies (step by step process)	TRL 3: analytical and experimental critical function or characteristic proof-of-concept	Tool		Knowledge & Understanding: Scientific breakthrough	Policy & Practice: Practice recommendation		X
T2.2 / D2.2 (VUB)	Guide to engage vulnerable groups in monitoring activities (repository of infosheets)	TRL 3: analytical and experimental critical function or characteristic proof-of-concept	Tool		Knowledge & Understanding: Scientific breakthrough			

T2.3 (UNIVDUN)	Best practices, methods, and guidelines for inclusive community labs - building of previous, and incorporating wider approaches to further methodological best practices	TRL 5: technology basic validation in a relevant environment	Guidelines	Community & local authority,	Methods & Processes: Significantly improved method		Exploiting previous learning around community pop-up labs --> methodological advancement, include more vulnerable groups in decision making. Engagement through science/comm unity interface	X
T2.3 (UNIVDUN)	Academic paper on community labs for research	TRL 5: technology basic validation in a relevant environment	Academic Paper	Academic	Knowledge & Understanding: Insight/knowledge advancement		Potential special issue	
ICCS_T3.3_D 3.3	Internet of Things (IoT) Platform	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Service	Public Authorities, Research Institutes, Health Agencies, Health Insurance Companies (B2G, B2B)	Products & Services: New service		Considered to be used as the core IoT platform of ICCS. Already in use in one EU Horizon Europe project.	
ICCS_T3.3_D 3.3	EcoPulse Citizen Participatory Digital Suite	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Web, Mobile app & Sensor	Citizens (B2C), Public Authorities, Research Institutes, Health Agencies, Health Insurance Companies (B2G, B2B)	Products & Services: New product	Products & Services: New service	Several functionalities of the Ecopulse mobile app are already in use in one EU Horizon Europe project.	X

ICCS_T3.3_D 3.3	Customised Low-cost Portable TRH sensor	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Sensor	Citizens (B2C), Public Authorities, Research Institutes, Health Agencies, Health Insurance Companies (B2G, B2B)	Products & Services: New product			X
CIBOS_T3.2_ D3.2	Tree registry app and administrative platform	TRL 6: technology model or prototype demonstration in a relevant environment	App &Web platform		Products & Services: New product			X
NOA__T3.3_D 3.3	Design of AQ monitoring network & Support of deployment	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Service		Products & Services: Significantly improved service			X
NOA__T3.3_D 3.3	AQ data retrieval, processing, QA QC, calibration back-end platform	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Data manageme nt platform		Methods & Processes: Significantly improved process			X
NOA__T3.3_D 3.3	Provision of AQ data online through API & front-end visualization platform	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Web platform		Products & Services: Significantly improved product			
CLS_T3.6_D3 .4	Tree Canopy map	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Data		Products & Services: Significantly improved product	Methods & Processes: Significantly improved method	Tree mapping	
IIASA - T3.2	Urban ReLeaf Cities Application	TRL 6: technology model or prototype demonstration in a relevant environment	Mobile app	Citizens, Public Authorities, Research Institutes	Products & Services: New product		Customized geolocated surveys for citizen engagement	X

MANN	Urban ReLeaf - Mannheim webpage (https://www.mannheim.de/de/service-bieten/mannheim-auf-klimakurs/projekte/urban-releaf) to inform citizens and encourage them to participate + two page on Mannheim's digital platform for citizen participation (https://mannheim-gemeinsam-gestalten.de/urban-releaf and https://mannheim-gemeinsam-gestalten.de/vorhaben/urban-releaf)	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Website		Other			
MANN	Activation of people to participate in the tree data collection through a broad activation campaign, resulting in 96 app registrations	TRL 9: actual technology qualified through successful mission operations.	Citizen activation		Products & Services: New product			
MANN	Establishing a new greening network with Urban ReLeaf as one of its topics (using the expertise, network and commitment of experts and stakeholders)		Citizen activation		Other			
MANN	(planned result) Information directly from the citizens about how Mannheim's squares should best be designed so that people can spend time there during hot weather (climate-adapted urban square design)		Data and information		Policy & Practice: Practice recommendation			
MANN	(planned result) comprehensive tree registry (valuable information about Mannheim's urban trees as a basis for planning, e.g. for		Data and information		Policy & Practice: Practice recommendation			

	replanting and planting new trees)							
UNIVDUN	Co-produced community greenspace map as part of Dundee What if Scenarios	TRL 5: technology basic validation in a relevant environment	Map	Local authority & community	Products & Services: Significantly improved product			
UTR	Participants gained insight into - awareness of temp differences - influence of environment on heat stress - confirmation of existing suspicions - personal discoveries (walking behaviour and new streets) - technical challenges		Citizens/ community	citizens, educational insitutions, public and pivate sector, environmental organisations, partners and stakeholders, general public				
UTR	- effect of neighbourhood design on heat stress - identifying hotspots		Linked to policy, design, principles for healthy urban living	Policy makers				
UTR	31000 observations on temp, humidity and hotspots enrich existing models, such as KNMI weather models, heat stress maps, urban tree canopies.		Data analyses	Research				
UTR	Data visualisation in the Digital Twin	TRL 9: actual technology qualified through successful mission operations.	Visualisaton	Policy makers				
UTR	planned: improving the sensor and app		Sensor					

UTR	planned: engage unusual suspects		Inclusivity					
DCC	Facilitate collaboration and discussion through partnership activities and events, leveraging these opportunities to enhance citizen engagement with green spaces throughout Dundee.		Partnership working, citizen engagement	Community		Policy & Practice: Policy recommendation	Products & Services: Significantly improved service	
DCC	Urban ReLeaf App - perceptions app, online & offline survey - perceptions of green spaces (movement, safety, space)	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Citizens, app, data gathering	citizens		other		Data gathering
DCC	Urban ReLeaf App - perceptions app, online & offline survey - wild grass	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Citizens, app, data gathering	citizens		other		Data gathering
DCC	Urban ReLeaf App - perceptions app, online & offline survey - SUDS	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Citizens, app, data gathering	citizens				Data gathering
DCC	Dundee Urban ReLeaf Newsletter	TRL 8: actual technology completed and qualified through test and demonstration	engagement, data and information	citizens, educational institutions, public and private sector, environmental organisations, partners and stakeholders, general public				Awareness and Engagement of the project
DCC	(planned) TRH sensors		data gathering					Not yet deployed
DCC	(planned) AQ sensors		data gathering					Not yet deployed

Riga	As part of the project, we have created thematic cooperation networks - the first with projects of similar content, the second with data gathering, storage and visualization competencies and responsibilities of players in the Riga city, the third with active residents and institutions that have adopted PM2.5 sensors and/or are interested to follow project activities.		engagement					
Riga	Low cost Air Quality (PM2,5) sensors (20) installed within institutions and citizens engagement		engagement, data gathering, analyse					
Riga	Information has been collected about datasets available in Riga that are and could potentially be used for the needs of Urban ReLeaf and similar projects.		engagement, data gathering, analyse					
Riga	TRH sensors (100) spreading among citizens and working (planned 2025)		engagement, data gathering, analyse					
Riga	Planned as general final result - A citizen-driven data ecosystem (climate monitoring system) has been created and tested in Riga		engagement, data gathering, analyse					
CASC	Urban ReLeaf App - perceptions app, online & offline survey	TRL 7: technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Citizens, app, data gathering	citizens	other		Data gathering	

WP5 Group3 CoP UNIVDUN	CoP: Urban design foresight for NBS and BGI scenario planning - Academic article on CoP workshop	TRL 5: technology basic validation in a relevant environment	Academic Paper	Science/policy/practice interface	Knowledge & Understanding: Insight/knowledge advancement			
WP5 Group3 CoP UNIVDUN	Output: Co-produced platform of enabling grey to green transition including tool select, exec sum for urban forecasting	TRL 5: technology basic validation in a relevant environment	Platform					
WP5 Group1 CoP ICLEI	Policy Brief: Triggering Innovation in Public Authorities with Citizen-Powered Science	TRL 3: analytical and experimental critical function or characteristic proof-of-concept	Policy brief	Local policy makers / citizen scientists	Policy & Practice: Policy recommendation			

AWAITING VALIDATION
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

T5.1 / D5.1	Urban ReLeaf MidTerm CoP Report	TRL 1: basic principles observed and reported	Report / CoP / Activities / Events / Workshops / Meetings / Achievements / Findings	Local government representatives, citizen associations, civil society organizations, business community, environmental scientists, geospatial technology specialists, statisticians, urban planning, architecture, environmental protection agencies, meteorological professionals, engagement officers, and NbS specialists	Policy & Practice: Policy change			
T5.2 / D5.2	Innovative governance model for data-driven and inclusive urban greening	TRL 3: analytical and experimental critical function or characteristic proof-of-concept	Governance / Framework / Model / Decision-making / Data Management / Inclusive / Citizen-Science	Local policy makers	Methods & Processes: New method			X

T5.3 / D5.3	Urban ReLeaf Toolkit and adoption roadmap	TRL 2: technology concept or application formulated	Toolkit / Innovative data governance / Social inclusion / Quality assurance / New data-streams / Adoption roadmap / Actionable pathways / Guidelines	Local authorities, CSOs, CS practitioners	Methods & Processes: New process			X
T5.4 / D5.4	Urban ReLeaf Accelerator Programme	TRL 2: technology concept or application formulated	Replication / Uptake / Upscaling / Webinars / Workshops	Local authorities	Other			

AWAITING VALUATION BY EUROPEAN COMMISSION

<p>T5.1 / D5.5</p>	<p>Urban ReLeaf Final CoP Report</p>	<p>TRL 1: basic principles observed and reported</p>	<p>Report / CoP / Activities / Events / Workshops / Meetings / Achievements / Findings</p>	<p>Local government representatives, citizen associations, civil society organizations, business community, environmental scientists, geospatial technology specialists, statisticians, urban planning, architecture, environmental protection agencies, meteorological professionals, engagement officers, and NbS specialists</p>	<p>Policy & Practice: Policy change</p>			
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AWAITING EUROPEAN

<p>UNIVDUN T6.1 / D6.1</p>	<p>Urban ReLeaf Website: Central hub for disseminating project information, results, and achievements.</p>	<p>TRL 9: actual technology qualified through successful mission operations.</p>	<p>Website, Archive</p>	<p>Academic, Research and Scientific Community, SME's and Industry, European and international networks, Government and public bodies, and policy makers, The general public, Press and Media. City stakeholders</p>	<p>Products & Services: New product</p>	<p>Products & Services: New service</p>	<p>It has potential for long-term impact beyond the project's duration. 1. Dissemination Platform, 2. Stakeholder Engagement 3. Knowledge Repository, 4. Impact measurement (analytics)</p>	
<p>UNIVDUN T6.2 / D6.1</p>	<p>Urban ReLeaf Brand: Serves as a visual representation of the project's identity, concept and values.</p>	<p>TRL 8: actual technology completed and qualified through test and demonstration</p>	<p>Brand, Communication</p>	<p>As above</p>	<p>Products & Services: New product</p>		<p>Potential for long-term impact and utility in exploitation activities</p>	
<p>UNIVDUN T6.1 / D6.1</p>	<p>Storytelling Strategy, Framework, Method and Tools to reach target audiences, including vulnerable communities</p>	<p>TRL 1: basic principles observed and reported</p>	<p>Storytelling</p>	<p>The general public, Academic, Research and Scientific Community, Government and public bodies, and policy makers</p>	<p>Methods & Processes: New process</p>			<p>X</p>

AWA
EUK

Appendix 3 Example canvases which are adapted for the bespoke Design for Business sprints.

